

Security analysis between Windows, Linux and macOS

Rizadette De La Cruz
School of Sciences and Engineering
University of Asia and the Pacific
Pasig City, Philippines
rizadette.delacruz@uap.asia

Abstract— The increasing reliance on technology has made computer security a critical concern. With the rise of various operating systems, the need for assessing their security features has become necessary. This research paper aims to compare and contrast the security features of Windows, Linux, and macOS. This paper also lists relevant security threats in the three operating systems and counter-measures to address them. The results show that relevant security threats among the three operating systems are malware, phishing attacks and denial of service. Counter-measures available that are common among them include: software update, user account and access control, firewalls and virus protection. In conclusion, while each operating system has its security strengths, there is no one-size-fits-all solution to security. Users must assess their security requirements and choose an operating system that best suits their needs.

Keywords—Windows, Linux, macOS, security, threats, counter-measure

I. INTRODUCTION

An operating system (OS) is a crucial component of any computing system, serving as the bridge between software applications and the underlying hardware. Some of the key functions of an operating system include managing the memory of the computer, controlling input and output devices, providing security, managing file systems and directories, managing user accounts, and providing a user interface for interaction with the computer [1].

There are several types of OS available in the market - Windows, macOS, Linux, Unix, and Android. Each operating system has its own unique features and strengths, depending on what the user focus is. Security, compatibility, portability, user interface are only some of the functionalities that a user will consider in choosing which type of operating system best suits their needs [2].

With the fast development of technology, comes risks associated in utilizing them. As such, security is one of the major things that users look into when they assess which kind of operating system they prefer [3]. As the bridge between software applications and hardware, OS are responsible for managing and protecting the computer's resources from potential threats, such as malware, viruses, and unauthorized access. The security of an operating system is very important as it can affect the security of the entire computing system, including sensitive data, applications, and networks. In recent years, OS have become the target of many cyberattacks, leading to significant data breaches and financial losses [4].

This paper aims to identify security features available in Windows, Linux and macOS. It also aims to identify relevant

security threats existing among the OS mentioned and identify the counter-measures to address those security threats.

II. RELATED LITERATURE

In comparing OS, there are several factors to consider, including graphical user interface (GUI), security, hardware compatibility, memory management, text mode interface, architecture, file system, portability and process management. OS preference varies depending on which factor is being considered [5].

According to the paper [5], windows is the most user friendly and has more hardware compatibility. In terms of security, Linux is the most secure among all OS given that it is an open-source operating system which gives users the ability to customize and implement security patches. As for memory management, macOS is the better option due to its fully integrated virtual memory system which is often on and continuously provides addressable space up to 4 per process. The virtual memory system allocates extra space for swap files on the root file system as a program uses space.

All available OS offer some level of security features such as firewalls, antivirus software, and encryption [6]. macOS has a level of security due to its unique operating system designed specifically for Apple devices with no third-party developers involved. Linux, being open source, is often regarded as more secure than Windows, which is a target of many malware attacks [7].

Security features common among operating systems are as follows [8]:

Identification and authentication: User identification and authentication is mandatory. Identification is that system needs the user's identity. And the process of connecting user identifier with the user is known as authentication.

Access Control: Computer system security's primary mechanism is access control. It consists of three steps. First is authorization, second is access permission and the third is impose access permission.

Least Privilege: Give all users, only the kind of privileges that they need to complete the task.

Trusted Channel: Usually in computers an interaction between the Operating system and a user is through middle application layer which is not trustworthy. So the operating system needs to make sure that during communication Trojan horse cannot capture the information.

Virus protection: In the real world, protecting your computer system from viruses is a very difficult task. In

general, certain functions can be protected using security MAC (Mandatory Access Control) mechanism of operating system security.

III. SECURITY IN WINDOWS, LINUX AND MACOS

Windows

Windows is the most widely marketed operating system as it is readily available upon purchase with minimal to no configuration required from its users. Its security model is a collection of user-mode and kernel-mode processes that deliver, monitor, and manage the different OS security components, and ensures finer granularity among them[5].

As it is a closed-source operating system, attacks and vulnerabilities are not easily addressed when they cannot be resolved by system measures and anti-virus installed within the computing system. Users would need to wait for Microsoft windows' patch to be released (if any) to resolve those attacks [7].

A closed-source OS (such as that of Windows and macOS) is where the source code is not accessible as compared to an open-source OS (Linux) [9].

Linux

The security model of Linux includes a series of many active processes, daemon utilities and libraries that provides its kernel with a stable environment to run in [5]. It is known for its robust security features that make it a popular choice for servers and other critical systems. It has a permission system that allows administrators to control who can access specific files and directories. Each file and directory has a set of permissions that specify which users and groups can read, write, or execute them. Being an open-source operating system, attacks can be easily addressed as anyone may review them which speeds up and simplifies the process of finding and fixing them [10].

macOS

macOS is known for its strong security features, which are designed to protect personal information, prevent malware attacks, and keep data safe. Apple, macOS' developer, is widely known for constantly releasing security patches to its devices to address security vulnerabilities. It supports user acknowledgement while executing any files [7].

IV. SECURITY THREATS IN OPERATING SYSTEMS

Below is a summary of relevant security threats among Windows, Linux and macOS:

Malware

Malware is any software that is designed to harm or exploit computer systems. It includes viruses, Trojans, and worms, and can be used to steal data, damage files, or take control of the system. A computer virus is a code that replicates when inserting into other programs. To be harmful to the OS, it needs an existing host program and spread them on a single computer system. Computer worm replicates itself by executing its code independent of any other program and spread through network connection to infect as many computer systems connected to the computer system as possible. A Trojan horse is a malware embedded in an application or system. The application or system would appear to perform some useful function but is performing some

unauthorized actions like capturing user information through keystrokes and sending it to a malicious host [11].

Trojans are the most popular type of malware that affect windows OS [12].

Phishing

Phishing is an attack that tries to delude the users by impersonating someone. Oftentimes, this type of attack is done through email that seems legitimate. However, these emails contain a malware file or insecure link that can compromise the sensitive data like passwords, usernames, etc. Some of the most common types of phishing listed below as referred to in [13].

Common phishing techniques are as follows [14]:

Similar spoofing: Cybercriminals spend more time and resources creating websites that seem just like the official ones. The phishing site's URL and the legitimate site's URL will be similar, and the user will be misled.

Invoice Phishing: An attacker sends an email to users claiming that they have an overdue invoice from a well-known vendor or firm, with a link to see it and pay the invoice.

Payment/ Delivery Scam: A credit card number and personal information are given to a well-known company to keep the user's payment information with them.

Downloads: Another common phishing technique is sending a fake email asking the recipient to open or download a document, usually asking the recipient to sign in.

Denial of Service (DoS)

DoS attacks aim to deny machine or network resources to certain users by interrupting the services of the host that are connected to the Internet. Such attacks are usually carried out by flooding a machine with unnecessary requests, overloading it, thus preventing the fulfillment of real requests [13].

DoS attack is an attempt to make a computer system or network unavailable by overwhelming it with traffic from multiple sources. Code Execution is a form of OS vulnerability that can lead to DoS. In code execution, an attacker is able to run an arbitrary code of their choosing with system level privileges on an OS or server that possesses the appropriate weakness [4].

DDoS attacks are similar, except that incoming requests to the victim now come from multiple sources (Distributed), making DDoS attacks more efficient, as it is almost impossible to block all target destinations of the attack. All of these attacks are usually a derivative of some specialized tools available on many Linux operating systems, or programming language packs that take advantage of the basic principles of network structures and their principles used in an OS [13].

V. COUNTER-MEASURES IN OPERATING SYSTEMS

Linux

Security measures in Linux are slim to none as it is a free OS to download. Along with being free, it is also considered open source. Being open-source means that anybody can take that OS and modify it to become their own. Being an open-source software, developers have to make everything accessible to allow modifications from other developers. This flexibility is advantageous for users to experiment on while in

the wrong hands become a threat due to its lack of security prevention functionality [6].

Countermeasures available in Linux [15]:

Security through Repositories: In Linux distributions, software is usually downloaded and installed from repositories, which hold a very large number of packages for users to download and use. Some software, like different display managers, are offered for almost all distributions, but some are more specific to certain ones. This method of installing software is generally seen as very safe because the creators of these Linux distributions approve of what repositories are allowed with the default shipment of the operating system. However, not everything is offered in repositories, such as Google's browser, Google Chrome. Though Chrome is a safe download, other programs may not be. Overall, users should refrain from installing software from the internet or from other sources as much as possible, and they should mainly install software from the repositories provided by the Linux distribution that they have decided to use.

Use of antivirus: ClamAV is a package within Linux repositories, or available from the ClamAV website, that scans files and directories for viruses and malware. Once ClamAV is installed, a variety of commands for configuring the antivirus can be accessible by the user. Schedules can be set for setting times for the antivirus to run, specific directories can be included or excluded from the scan, and different types of scans can be done on the system. In addition, individual files and directories can be scanned outside of a scheduled scan by specifying the file or directory with the command to run it. Daemons can be installed for both running the system scan and for updating the database of known viruses in the background.

Updating Software: In order to keep specific software and packages secure, they should be updated regularly. This can assure that software has the latest security patches so exploits are abused. In order to keep a Linux system safe, both downloaded programs and system packages should be updated. This can be done by either going to the website where the software was downloaded and installing the updated versions, or using the terminal to run distribution-specific commands to update everything that was downloaded from the repositories, such as an updated browser or an updated kernel.

Firewalls: In order to prevent attacks from computers on the same network, firewalls can be set up. A firewall is a set of rules that lists what ports are open to outside machines and what the local machine can send to other machines. Using the iptables package available in most Linux repositories, rules can be set to prevent attacks like these.

Passwords management: When a Linux distribution is installed on a system, users are usually prompted to set up a user account, which creates a directory for all the files for that user within the filesystem. These files shall be kept separate from the root user to prevent either the accidental or intentional deletion of important system files of the user. In addition, if multiple people use the same machine, different accounts shall be made for each person using it. This isolation will allow individual user files separate from each other and will also keep the files inaccessible to anyone that does not know the account password. The root password and the user password shall be different from each other. This can prevent

anyone from either gaining access to a user to gaining access to the root account by only knowing one password.

File access Permissions: In order to prevent other users on a machine from gaining access to files that they should not have access to, different permissions must be set on a machine. These can be done with commands like chmod. In addition, groups of users can be made so permissions can be set for multiple users at once using the chgrp command. Setting permissions for who can read, write, or execute files will prevent users from manipulating or executing files, and possibly changing the system in ways that they should not.

Windows

Microsoft Windows is the world's most popular consumer operating system. It is used as a standard in many office environments. But at the same time, this popularity makes it a target for malware. Windows is a closed source operating system where the users or security community doesn't have access to the source code [16].

Countermeasures available in Windows OS [14]:

Secure Boot UEFI: The integrity of each boot process component is checked before the operating system is loaded. Only trusted OS bootloaders can be loaded on computers with UEFI firmware and a Trusted Platform Module (TPM).

Updates: The most recent operating system updates should be installed.

Data Backup: This can help prevent delay, data loss, and financial loss in case of a cyber-attack.

Exchange Online Protection: It utilizes many levels of spam filtering and provides a variety of spam filtering features, including bulk mail and international spam. It assists in protecting email, files, and internet storage against viruses.

Limited Access to Folders: It protects ransomware from encrypting data and keeps users for ransom by limiting file and folder access.

Awareness

Regular OS patch updates

Monitor network traffic via a firewall.

Enforcement of secure access via least privileges and user restrictions

macOS

Apple claims that macOS is built on a proprietary infrastructure that does not allow any unknown developers to access its integrated system files. As a result, these machines are not as customizable as they would be if they were a Windows or a Linux machine, but it seems this is a common trend. The less customizable a machine is, the better security measures it has. More user customization ultimately results in more loopholes for unwanted guests [6].

macOS is very unique compared to the rest as they are specifically designed for Apple devices. There is no third-party developer. As a result, MAC has a strong shield around it that protects the OS from malwares and viruses. Along with this, MAC also supports the user acknowledgement while executing any files. Apple regularly releases updates for Mac OS to enhance the security [16].

CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORKS

Comparing security functionality between Windows, Linux, and macOS typically provides users with a general idea of the strengths and weaknesses of each. Windows is the most widely used operating system in the world, which makes it a popular target for cyberattacks. However, Microsoft has made significant strides in recent years to improve its security features and patch vulnerabilities quickly. Linux is known for its strong security model, as it is based on open source software that can be audited by the community for vulnerabilities. However, Linux distributions can vary in terms of security features and configuration. macOS is generally considered to be a more secure operating system than Windows. However, like any operating system, it is still vulnerable to attacks and needs to be updated and configured properly to maintain security.

Ultimately, the choice of operating system depends on the user's needs and preferences, as well as the specific security risks they face. It is important to keep all operating systems up to date with the latest security patches and to implement best practices for security.

REFERENCES

- [1] Tiwari, Ravikant & Siddiqui, Dr-Shadab. (2021). ANALYTICAL SURVEY OF WINDOWS OPERATING SYSTEM AND COMPARISON OF WINDOWS, LINUX AND ANDROID OPERATING SYSTEM. *International Journal of Engineering Applied Sciences and Technology*. 6. 10.33564/IJEAST.2021.v06i02.028.
- [2] Adekotoju, Akinlolu & Odumabo, Adedoyin & Ademola, Adedokun & Aiyeniko, Olukayode. (2020). A Comparative Study of Operating Systems: Case of Windows, UNIX, Linux, Mac, Android and iOS. *International Journal of Computer Applications*. 176. 16-23. 10.5120/ijca2020920494.
- [3] Rath, Plawan & Anil, G.. (2012). Proposed Challenges And Areas of Concern in Operating System Research and Development. *International Journal of Computer Science Issues*. 9.
- [4] Softic, Jasmin & Vejzović, Zanin. (2022). Operating Systems Vulnerability – An Examination of Windows 10, macOS, and Ubuntu from 2015 to 2021. *Advances in Science, Technology and Engineering Systems Journal*. 7. 230-235. 10.25046/aj070625.
- [5] Odun-Ayo, Isaac & Okokpujie, Kennedy & Oputa, Kingsley & Okuazun, Gideon & Ogbu, Henry & Emmanuel, Franklin & Shofadekan, Ayobami. (2021). Comparative Study of Operating System Quality Attributes. *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering*. 1107. 10.1088/1757-899X/1107/1/012061.
- [6] G. J. Ruiz, M. M. Chowdhury and S. Latif, "A Comparative Study of OS Security," 2021 International Conference on Electrical, Computer, Communications and Mechatronics Engineering (ICECCME), Mauritius, Mauritius, 2021, pp. 01-06, doi: 10.1109/ICECCME52200.2021.9590921.
- [7] Sarki Abubakar, Maryam. (2021). A Comparative Analysis of Operating System: case study of Windows Operating and Mackintosh Operating System.
- [8] Shah, Munam & Sajid, Afifa & Kamran, Muhammad & Javaid, Qaisar & Zhang, Sijing. (2016). An Analysis on Host Vulnerability Evaluation of Modern Operating Systems. *International Journal of Advanced Computer Science and Applications (IJACSA)*. 7. 245-254. 10.14569/IJACSA.2016.070430.
- [9] Hasnain, Sk & Rafi, Anwar. (2019). Windows, Linux, Mac Operating System and Decision Making. *International Journal of Computer Applications*. 177. 11-15. 10.5120/ijca2019919725.
- [10] Annmary Shaji, Elizabeth Jaison, Gibin George. (2021). A Study on Security Evaluation in Linux. *International Conference on Intellectual Property Rights*, 20/02/2021
- [11] Naseer, Muchammad & Rusdi, Jack & Shanono, Nuruddeen & Salam, Sazilah & Zulkiflee, M. & Abu, Nur & Abadi, Iwan. (2021). Malware Detection: Issues and Challenges. *Journal of Physics: Conference Series*. 1807. 012011. 10.1088/1742-6596/1807/1/012011.
- [12] Hamdani, Syed Wasif Abbas & Abbas, Haider & Janjua, Abdul & Shahid, Waleed & Amjad, Muhammad & Malik, Jahanzaib & Murtaza, Malik & Atiquzzaman, Mohammed & Khan, Abdul. (2021). Cybersecurity Standards in the Context of Operating System: Practical Aspects, Analysis, and Comparisons. *ACM Computing Surveys*. 54. 1-36. 10.1145/3442480.
- [13] Fountas, Panagiotis & Taxiarchis, Kouskouras & Georgios, Kranas & Maglaras, Leandros & Ferrag, Mohamed Amine. (2021). Intrusion Detection in Critical Infrastructures: A Literature Review. *Smart Cities*. 4. 1146-1157. 10.3390/smartsities4030061.
- [14] Rijah, Muhammed & Rajapaksha, Samantha. (2023). Security Issues and Challenges in Windows OS Level. 07. 19-25.
- [15] Yaswinski, Matthew & Chowdhury, Md & Jochen, Mike. (2019). Linux Security: A Survey. 357-362. 10.1109/EIT.2019.8834112.
- [16] Thangavel, Roshini Pinto, Karen & Maiti, Ankita & Dh, Tamil. (2019). Comparative Research on Recent Trends, Designs, and Functionalities of Various Operating Systems. *International Journal of Engineering and Technical Research*. 8.